

KVADRATIK CHEGIRMALAR, LEJANDR SIMVOLI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada sonlar sonlar nazariyasida muhim hisoblangan kvadratik chegirmalar haqida muhim teoremlar va ularning tatbiqi, jumladan Lejandr simvoli, Eyler kriteriyasi, Gauss lemmasi keltirilgan. Masalalar va ularning yechimlari batafsil tushuntirilgan. Mustaqil yechish uchun yetarlicha masalalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tub son, murakkab son, kvadratik chegirma, taqqoslama, Lejandr simvoli, Ferma teoremasi.

ABSTRACT

This article presents important theorems about quadratic deductions, which are considered important in number theory, and their applications, including Legendre's symbol, Euler's criterion, Gauss's lemma. The issues and their solutions are explained in detail. Sufficient problems are given for independent solution.

Key words: prime number, Composite number, quadratic reciprocity, module, Legendre's symbol, Fermat's theorem.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье представлены важные теоремы о квадратичных выводах, которые считаются важными в теории чисел, и их приложения, включая символ Лежандра, критерий Эйлера, лемму Гаусса. Подробно описаны проблемы и пути их решения. Приведено достаточное количество задач для самостоятельного решения.

Ключевые слова: простое число, составное число, модуль, квадратичная взаимность, Символ Лежандра, теорема Ферма.

Dastlab quyidagi tushunchalarni kiritib olamiz:

Ta'rif 1. a va m butun sonlar o'zaro tub bo'lsin. Agar $x^2 \equiv a \pmod{m}$ taqqoslama yechimga ega bo'ladigan x butun son mavjud bo'lsa, u holda a , mod m bo'yicha **kvadratik chegirma** deyiladi.

O‘zaro tub bo‘lgan p tub son va a butun son uchun quyidagicha funksiya aniqlaymiz:

$$\left(\frac{a}{p}\right) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{agar } a - \text{mod } p \text{ bo'yicha kvadratik chegirma bo'lsa} \\ -1, & \text{aks holda} \end{cases}$$

Ta’rif 2. Yuqorida o‘zaro tub bo‘lgan p tub son va a butun sonlar uchun aniqlangan $\left(\frac{a}{p}\right)$ funksiyaga **Lejandr simvoli** deyiladi.

Kiritilgan tushunchalarga ko‘ra quyidagi teorami ko‘ramiz.

Teorema 1. $p \geq 3$ tub son. $\{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$ top‘lamda $\frac{p-1}{2}$ ta $\text{mod } p$ bo‘yicha kvadratik chegirma mavjud.

Isbot: Aytaylik o‘zaro teng bo‘lmagan $i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, \frac{p-1}{2}\}$ sonlar uchun $i^2 \equiv j^2 \pmod{p}$ bo‘lsin, u holda $p \mid (i-j)(i+j)$, lekin $i+j < p$ demak $p \mid i-j \Rightarrow i=j$, bu esa ziddiyat.

$$k^2 \equiv m_k \pmod{p} \text{ bo'lsin, bunda } k = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{p-1}{2}.$$

Bundan ko‘rinadiki $(p-k)^2 \equiv k^2 \pmod{p} \equiv m_k \pmod{p}$ U holda $m_1, m_2, \dots, m_{\frac{p-1}{2}}$ sonlari $\text{mod } p$ bo‘yicha kvadratik chegirmalar bo‘ladi va ular turli xil. Shuningdek ular soni $\frac{p-1}{2}$ ta. ■

Lejandr simvoliga oid ushbu xossalarni ko‘rib o‘tamiz.

1-xossa. Eyler Kriteriyasi: Agar p toq tub son va $(a, p) = 1$ bo‘lsa, u holda

$$a^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{p}\right) \pmod{p} \text{ taqqoslama o‘rinli bo‘ladi.}$$

Isboti: Xossani kki holatga ajratib isbotlaymiz.

1-holat: Agar $\left(\frac{a}{p}\right) = 1$ bo‘lsa, u holda $i^2 \equiv a \pmod{p}$ taqqoslama yechimga ega va $(i, p) = 1$.

Fermaning kichik teoremasiga ko‘ra [1] $1 \equiv i^{p-1} = (i^2)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \equiv a^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \pmod{p}$, shuningdek $\left(\frac{a}{p}\right) = 1$. Demak $a^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{p}\right) \pmod{p}$.

2-holat: Agar $\left(\frac{a}{p}\right) = -1$ bo‘lsa, $i^2 \equiv a \pmod{p}$ taqqoslama yechimga ega emas.

Ixtiyoriy $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$ uchun, yagona $i' \in \{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$ son mavjudki bunda $ii' \equiv a \pmod{p}$. Shuningdek $i \neq i'$.

Demak $\{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$ to'plamni $\frac{p-1}{2}$ ta (i, i') juftliklarga ajrata olamiz.

Vilson teoremasiga ko'ra [2], $-1 \equiv (p-1)! \equiv (ii')^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \equiv a^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \pmod{p}$

Bundan esa $a^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \equiv -1 \pmod{p} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{p}\right) \pmod{p}$. ■

2-xossa. Agar $a \equiv b \pmod{p}$ bo'lsa, u holda $\left(\frac{a}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{b}{p}\right)$ tenglik o'rinli bo'ladi.

3-xossa. Multiplikativlik: p toq tub son va a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n butun sonlar uchun $\left(\frac{a_1 a_2 \dots a_n}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{a_1}{p}\right) \left(\frac{a_2}{p}\right) \dots \left(\frac{a_n}{p}\right)$ tenglik o'rinli bo'ladi.

4-xossa. Ixtiyoriy p tub soni uchun, $\left(\frac{-1}{p}\right) = (-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}}$ tenglik o'rinli.

Ushbu xossalar Eyler kiriteriyasi hamda ta'rif orqali sodda isbotlanadi.

Aytaylik, a natural soni p tub songa bo'linmasin. U holda quyidagi bo'linish algoritmini qaraylik: $ka = pq_k + r_k$ bunda $k = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{p-1}{2}$.

Aytaylik b_1, b_2, \dots, b_m sonlari turli va $r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{\frac{p-1}{2}}$ qoldiqlar ichida $\frac{p}{2}$ dan kichik qoldiqlar bo'lsin.

c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n sonlari esa turli va $r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{\frac{p-1}{2}}$ qoldiqlar ichida $\frac{p}{2}$ dan katta qoldiqlar bo'lsin.

Endi ushbu ajratilgan qoldiqlar guruhidagi qoldiqlar soniga doir quyidagi lemmani ko'ramiz:

Lemma 1. (Gauss [3]) a natural soni p tub songa bo'linmasin. n yuqorida aniqlangan $r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{\frac{p-1}{2}}$ qoldiqlar ichida $\frac{p}{2}$ dan katta turli qoldiqlar soni.

U holda, bu sonlar uchun $\left(\frac{a}{p}\right) = (-1)^n$ tenglik o'rinli.

Isbot. $\frac{p}{2} < c_j \leq p-1$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ bundan $1 \leq p - c_j \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$.

Shuningdek $p - c_j \neq b_i$ bunda $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ va $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$.

Chunki agar $c_j + b_i = p$ bo'lsa, $p = as - pq_s + at - pq_t \Rightarrow p \mid s + t$ bu esa ziddiyat, chunki $1 \leq s, t \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$.

Bundan kelib chiqadiki, $\{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_m, p - c_1, p - c_2, \dots, p - c_n\} = \{1, 2, \dots, \frac{p-1}{2}\}$

$$\prod_{i=1}^m b_i \prod_{j=1}^n c_j = \prod_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} r_k = \prod_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} (ka - pq_k) \equiv \prod_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} ka = a^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \left(\frac{p-1}{2}\right)! \pmod{p}$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^m b_i \prod_{j=1}^n (p - c_j) = \left(\frac{p-1}{2}\right)!$$

Ikkinchi

tomondan

esa

$$\prod_{i=1}^m b_i \prod_{j=1}^n (p - c_j) \equiv (-1)^n \prod_{i=1}^m b_i \prod_{j=1}^n c_j \equiv (-1)^n a^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \left(\frac{p-1}{2}\right)! \pmod{p}$$

Bundan ko'rinadiki, $a^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod{p} \Rightarrow a^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \equiv (-1)^n \pmod{p}$.

Eyler kriteriyasiga ko'ra $\left(\frac{a}{p}\right) \equiv a^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \equiv (-1)^n \pmod{p} \Rightarrow \left(\frac{a}{p}\right) = (-1)^n$. ■

Ushbu lemmadan kelib chiqadigan bir nechta natijalarni keltiramiz:

Natija 1. Barcha p toq tub sonlar uchun $\left(\frac{2}{p}\right) = (-1)^{\frac{p^2-1}{8}}$ tenglik o'rinli.

Isbot. Gauss lemmasiga ko'ra $a = 2$ da

$$\{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{(p-1)/2}\} = \{2, 4, \dots, p-1\} \Rightarrow n = \left[\frac{p}{2}\right] - \left[\frac{p}{4}\right]$$

Agar $p = 4l + 1$ bo'lsa, u holda $n = 2l - l = l$ va $\frac{p^2-1}{8} = 2l^2 + l$.

Agar $p = 4l + 3$ bo'lsa, u holda $n = 2l + 1 - l = l + 1$ va $\frac{p^2-1}{8} = 2l^2 + 3l + 1$.

Bundan kelib chiqadiki $\frac{p^2-1}{8} \equiv n \pmod{2}$, ya'ni $\left(\frac{2}{p}\right) = (-1)^n = (-1)^{\frac{p^2-1}{8}}$. ■

Natija 2. p va q turli toq tub sonlar bo'lsin, u holda bu sonlar uchun

$$\left(\frac{p}{q}\right) \left(\frac{q}{p}\right) = (-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2} \cdot \frac{q-1}{2}}$$
 tenglik o'rinli bo'ladi.

Yuqorida keltirilgan teorema va lemmalardan foydalanib bir nechta masalalarni yechimi bilan keltiramiz.

1-Masala. k soni $k = 2^{2^n} + 1$ ko‘rinishda ifodalanadi, bunda n - natural son. U holda shuni isbotlangki, k tub son bo‘lishi uchun $k \mid 3^{\frac{k-1}{2}} + 1$ munosabat o‘rinli bo‘lishi zarur va yetarli.

Yechim. Yetarliligi: Agar $k \mid 3^{\frac{k-1}{2}} + 1$ bo‘lsa, $k \mid 3^{k-1} - 1$ o‘rinli bo‘ladi.

Demak, $o_k(3) \mid k - 1 = 2^{2^n}$ ammo $o_k(3) \nmid \frac{k-1}{2} = 2^{2^n-1} \Rightarrow o_k(3) = 2^{2^n} = k - 1$.

Shuningdek $k - 1 = o_k(3) \mid \varphi(k) \Rightarrow \varphi(k) \geq k - 1$ bundan kelib chiqadiki k tub son.

Zarurligi: Agar k tub son bo‘lsa, u holda Lejandr simvoli xossalariga ko‘ra

$$\left(\frac{3}{k}\right) \left(\frac{k}{3}\right) = (-1)^{\frac{k-1}{2}} = 1 \Rightarrow \left(\frac{3}{k}\right) = \left(\frac{k}{3}\right) = \left(\frac{2}{3}\right) = -1.$$

Eyler kriteriyasiga ko‘ra $3^{\frac{k-1}{2}} \equiv \left(\frac{3}{k}\right) \equiv -1 \pmod{k} \Rightarrow k \mid 3^{\frac{k-1}{2}} + 1$. ■

2-Masala [4]. Agar $a^2 + b^2$ ko‘rinishdagi sonning $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ ko‘rinishidagi tub bo‘luvchisi mavjud bo‘lsa, u holda $p \mid a$ va $p \mid b$.

Yechim: Faraz qilaylik $p \nmid a$ yoki $p \nmid b$ bo‘lsin. U holda $(a, p) = (b, p) = 1$ bundan

$a^2 \equiv -b^2 \pmod{p} \Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{a^2}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{-b^2}{p}\right)$ va multiplikativlikga ko‘ra

$$1 = \left(\frac{a}{p}\right) \left(\frac{a}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{a^2}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{b^2}{p}\right) \left(\frac{-1}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{b}{p}\right) \left(\frac{b}{p}\right) \left(\frac{-1}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{-1}{p}\right) = (-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}}$$

Demak $4 \mid p - 1$ ammo $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ ziddiyat, ya’ni farazimiz xato ekan. ■

3-Masala [4]. Agar a va b butun son va p tub son uchun $p \mid a^2 + ab + b^2$ va $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ bo‘lsa, isbotlang $p \mid a$ va $p \mid b$.

Yechim. Teskarisini faraz qilaylik $p \nmid a$ yoki $p \nmid b$ bo‘lsin.

U holda $(a, p) = (b, p) = 1$ bo‘ladi. Shuningdek

$$p \mid a^2 + ab + b^2 \Rightarrow p \mid 4(a^2 + ab + b^2) = 4a^2 + 4ab + 4b^2 = (2a + b)^2 + 3b^2 \\ \Rightarrow (2a + b)^2 \equiv -3b^2 \pmod{p}$$

Demak multiplikativlik xossadiga ko‘ra

$$\left(\frac{-3b^2}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{-3}{p}\right) \left(\frac{b}{p}\right) \left(\frac{b}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{-3}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{-1}{p}\right) \left(\frac{3}{p}\right) = 1 \text{ va } \left(\frac{3}{p}\right) \left(\frac{p}{3}\right) = (-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}}.$$

Bu tengliklardan $1 = \left(\frac{-1}{p}\right) \left(\frac{3}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{-1}{p}\right) \left(\frac{p}{3}\right) (-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} = \left(\frac{p}{3}\right)$ ni hosil qilamiz ammo $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{p}{3}\right) = \left(\frac{2}{3}\right) = -1$ bu esa ziddiyat.

Demak farazimiz xato ekan. Bundan esa $p \mid a$ va $p \mid b$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi. ■

4-Masala. (IMO 1996). Agar a va b natural sonlar uchun $15a + 16b$ va $16a - 15b$ sonlarining ikkalasi ham to'la kvadrat bo'lsa, $\sqrt{31a + b}$ ifodaning eng kichik qiymatini toping.

Yechim: Shartga ko'ra $15a + 16b = x^2$ va $16a - 15b = y^2$ tengliklarni qanoatlantiradigan x va y nomanfiy butun sonlar mavjud.

Demak $a = \frac{15x^2 + 16y^2}{481}$ va $b = \frac{16x^2 - 15y^2}{481}$ ya'ni $13 \cdot 37 \mid 15x^2 + 16y^2 \Rightarrow$

$$15x^2 \equiv -16y^2 \pmod{13} \Rightarrow 2x^2 \equiv -3y^2 \pmod{13} \Rightarrow x^2 \equiv 5y^2 \pmod{13}.$$

Agar $(x, 13) = 1$ yoki $(y, 13) = 1$ bo'lsa, u holda

$$\left(\frac{5}{13}\right) = \left(\frac{13}{5}\right) (-1)^{\frac{5-1}{2} \cdot \frac{13-1}{2}} = \left(\frac{13}{5}\right) = \left(\frac{3}{5}\right) = \left(\frac{5}{3}\right) (-1)^{\frac{5-1}{2} \cdot \frac{3-1}{2}} = \left(\frac{5}{3}\right) = \left(\frac{2}{3}\right) = -1$$

Bu esa ziddiyat. Demak $13 \mid x$ va $13 \mid y$. (*)

Xuddi shunday $15x^2 \equiv -16y^2 \pmod{37} \Rightarrow 30x^2 \equiv -32y^2 \pmod{37} \Rightarrow$

$$30x^2 \equiv -5y^2 \pmod{37} \Rightarrow -6x^2 \equiv y^2 \pmod{37}.$$

Agar $(x, 37) = 1$ yoki $(y, 37) = 1$ bo'lsa, u holda

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{-6}{37}\right) &= \left(\frac{-1}{37}\right) \left(\frac{2}{37}\right) \left(\frac{3}{37}\right) = (-1)^{\frac{37-1}{2}} \cdot (-1)^{\frac{37^2-1}{8}} \cdot \left(\frac{3}{37}\right) = (-1) \cdot \left(\frac{3}{37}\right) = \\ &= (-1) \cdot \left(\frac{37}{3}\right) (-1)^{\frac{3-1}{2} \cdot \frac{37-1}{2}} = (-1) \cdot \left(\frac{37}{3}\right) = (-1) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) = -1 \text{ bu ham ziddiyat.} \end{aligned}$$

Demak $37 \mid x$ va $37 \mid y$. (**)

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U holda (*) va (**) ga ko'ra $481 \mid x$ va $481 \mid y$.

$$\text{Demak } \sqrt{31a + b} = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} \geq \sqrt{2 \cdot 481^2} = 481\sqrt{2}.$$

Tenglik esa $a = 31 \cdot 481$ va $b = 481$ da o'rinli bo'ladi. Javob: $481\sqrt{2}$. ■

Mustaqil yechish uchun masalalar:

5-Masala. (Vetnam TST). $2^n + 1$ ko‘rinishidagi sonning $8k + 7$ ko‘rinishidagi tub bo‘luvchisi mavjud emasligini isbotlang.

6-Masala. (Gazeta Matematica). Agar p tub son uchun $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ tenglik o‘rinli bo‘lsa, u holda $x_1^p + x_2^p + x_3^p + \dots + x_n^p + 1 = (x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots + x_n)^2$ tenglama butun sonlarda yechimga ega emasligini isbotlang.

7-Masala. Tenglamani natural sonlarda yeching: $10^n + 89 = x^2$.

8-Masala. Tenglamani tub sonlarda yeching: $p^2 - pq - q^3 = 1$.

9-Masala. (Danube matematika musobaqasi-2016) $n \in N$ son uchun $f(n) = \left(\frac{n}{1} + 1\right) \left(\frac{n}{2} + 2\right) \dots \left(\frac{n}{n} + n\right)$ funksiya berilgan. Agar $S = \{n \mid f(n) \in N\}$ bo‘lsa, u holda S -chekli to‘plam ekanligini isbotlang.

10-Masala. (Mathematical Reflections). Berilgan p tub son uchun $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ va $2^p \equiv 2 \pmod{p^2}$ tengliklar o‘rinli. Agar q soni $2^p - 1$ ning tub bo‘luvchisi bo‘lsa, u holda $2^q > (6p)^p$ bo‘lishini isbotlang

11-Masala. a - natural son. Agar $\forall p > n$ uchun $\binom{a}{p} = 1$ bo‘ladigan n natural soni mavjud bo‘lsa, u holda a to‘la kvadrat ekanligini isbotlang.

12-Masala. (IMO-2008). $n^2 + 1$ sonining $2n + \sqrt{2n}$ sonidan katta tub bo‘luvchisi mavjud bo‘ladigan n natural sonlar cheksiz ko‘p ekanligini isbotlang.

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